

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**EFFECTS OF HIGH INTENSITY INTERVAL TRAINING AND
MODERATE INTENSITY CONTINUOUS TRAINING ON
CARDIOVASCULAR ENDURANCE IN YOUNG HEALTHY
FEMALES**¹Dr Irum Ali, ²Dr Aroosa Ishfaq, ³Dr Munazzah Qasim, ⁴Dr Sidra Majeed¹School of Rehabilitation Sciences, The University of Faisalabad.

Article Received: October 2020

Accepted: November 2020

Published: December 2020

Abstract:

Objectives: To compare the effects of high intensity interval training VS moderate intensity continuous training on the cardiovascular endurance in young healthy females.

Method: 30 young healthy females were collected and randomly assigned into two training groups HIIT and MICT, each group having a sample size of (n=15). There will be three parameters to be tested including (VO₂max, Resting heart rate, Rate perceived exertion). Each group will be tested at three different times e.g. (at Baseline measurement, after two weeks and after four weeks). For first two weeks HIIT group have to perform at 70%HRR and for third and fourth weeks at 75%HRR for two minutes followed by active resting interval at 30%HRR for two minutes (1:1) with warm up and cool down period (2 minutes each period) on treadmill. For first two weeks, the MICT group has to perform at 40%HRR and for third and fourth weeks at 50% HRR for fifteen minutes continuously on treadmill including warm up and cool down period (2 minutes each period).

Result: The final assessment of HIIT and MICT groups had shown p values for VO₂max (p=.000), RHR (p=.323) and for RPE (p=.085). These values indicating significant improvement in these three parameters in both groups.

Conclusion: This study showed that there were significant improvements in both groups but there were more improvements in VO₂max in HIIT group so, it is proved that HIIT is more beneficial than MICT in improving cardiovascular endurance.

Keywords: HIIT, MICT, RPE, RHR, Cardiovascular endurance.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Irum Ali,**

School of Rehabilitation Sciences, The University of Faisalabad.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Irum Ali et al, *Effects Of High Intensity Interval Training And Moderate Intensity Continuous Training On Cardiovascular Endurance In Young Healthy Females.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Cardiovascular endurance increases VO_2 max (increase level of oxygen uptake). VO_2 max is the most authentic indicator of enhanced cardiovascular endurance. The mechanism behind the cardiovascular endurance is that as the VO_2 max increases in response to high intensity interval training (HIIT), there will be parallel increase in the size and contraction of myocardial cells. Myocardial contraction depends on the availability of calcium that increases with regular exercise. This calcium assists in increased myocardial contraction (Pelliccia, *et al.*, 2002).

There is a direct relationship between cardiac output and exercise intensity. As the number of cardiac beats increase in response to exercise intensity, there will be a parallel increase in ejection fraction. During vigorous physical activity, there is redistribution of blood that result in reduced splanchnic circulation and enhanced circulation toward working muscles to meet their metabolic demands (Wilmore and Costil, 2005). In the modern era, The new technological advances fascinating the people and diverting them toward a more sedentary life style than earlier (Dupont, *et al.*, 2003).

With the passage of time, the involvement in physical activity is decreasing due to revolutions in the field of technology and increasing the risk factors for future diseases due to inactivity (Aghalinejad and Gharakhanloo, 2005).

Now it is prioritized to increase the awareness of benefits of physical activity on health and in the prevention of disease at public level (Burgomaster, *et al.*, 2008).

The purpose of WHO is to enhance the awareness of people about importance of physical activity how it play an important role in the prevention of heart problems, psychological disorders and metabolic disorders (Cook, *et al.*, 2003).

Regular exercise is necessary to promote health, play an important role in the prevention of diseases with advancing age and slowing the aging process. These diseases include Mostly the musculoskeletal pathologies, Heart diseases and psychological issues etc. (Arena, *et al.*, 2007).

High intensity interval training includes a training protocol of working at high intensity followed by a period of low intensity or a rest interval. The working

intervals and recovery intervals are of different durations (Cahill, 2014).

Moderate intensity continuous training is the workout that is performed at 70_75%HRmax (Medicine and Ehrman, 2010).

SUBJECT AND METHOD:

This randomized control trial has been conducted by taking sample of female population at Bhatti gym and University hostel gym Faisalabad over four months.

Thirty young healthy females with mean age 24.47 ± 4.091 years were selected on the basis of inclusion criteria and demonstration was given to all the participants about the whole training protocol. The consent form was signed from all the participants prior to baseline assessment. Inclusion criteria include young healthy females having age 20-36years, having score of at least 15 on rate perceived exertion scale and having aVO_2 max value ranges between 31.0-34.9mg/kg/min according to Bruce protocol formula for women. Exclusion criteria include females having any systemic disease, taking part in other fitness programs, not taking any kind of medication on regular basis and pregnant females.

They were recruited and randomly assigned into two groups as high intensity interval training (HIIT) and moderate intensity continuous training (MICT) groups each with a sample size of (n=15). Before participation into the training program baseline assessment was done of all participants that include the following parameters i.e. VO_2 max, rate of perceived exertion and resting heart rate.

The resting heart rate was measured by pulse oximeter of all the participants at three different times i.e. at baseline measurement, after two weeks and after four weeks to see changes in resting heart rate within four weeks.

The heart rate reserve of each participant was calculated by karvonen's formula, Exercise HR = % of target intensity $(HR_{max} - HR_{rest}) + HR_{rest}$. VO_2 max: It was calculated by performing graded exercise test on treadmill according to Bruce protocol. The total test time was 27 minutes and test has nine stages. The participant has to perform for 3 minutes at each stage and then total time was calculated the participant has spent on treadmill. This time value was then put into Bruce protocol formula for estimating VO_2 max. The VO_2 max was calculated at each measurement i.e. at baseline measurement, after two weeks and after four

weeks to find out improvement in cardiovascular endurance.

The Bruce formula for calculating $VO_2\text{max}$ for females is $VO_2\text{ max} = 4.38 \times T - 3.9$, T = Total time on the treadmill measured as a fraction of a minute (i. e A test time of 10minutes 30 seconds would be written as T=10.30).

Rate perceived exertion was also measured at the end of graded exercise tests at three different times i.e. at baseline measurement, after two weeks and after four weeks by showing the participants Borg's rating of perceived exertion scale 6-20. The value 6 rates for "no exertion", 14-15 rating for "moderate exertion" and 20 for "maximal exertion. Participants have to categorize the values in order to find out the exertion level.

All the participants included in the study were also use Stepper for five minutes, cycling for five minutes and Vibrator for ten minutes in both groups i.e. HIIT and MICT after completing the basic training protocol at treadmill.

The high intensity interval training group (n=15) was given exercise program, for first two weeks they have to perform at 70%HRR for two minutes followed by active resting interval at 30%HRR for two minutes (1:1) with warm up and cool down period (2 minutes each) on treadmill. There were four repetitions per session and four consecutive sessions per week. After two weeks of intervention, measurements of all parameters of study were also documented carefully. At third and fourth week, the exercise intensity was increased. Participants have to perform at 75%HRR for two minute alternating with 30%HRR (1:1) for next two weeks followed by warm up and cool down period (2 minutes each). There were three repetitions per session and four consecutive sessions per week. At the end of fourth week or at final assessment the results were documented of all the parameters including $VO_2\text{max}$, Resting heart rate and Rating perceived exertion of all participants.

For first two weeks, the MICT group had to perform at 40%HRR for fifteen minutes continuously on treadmill including warm up and cool down period (2 minutes each) for first two weeks. After two weeks, measurements of all study parameters were also taken. At third and fourth week exercise intensity was increased. Participants have to perform at 50%HRR for fifteen minutes on treadmill continuously including warm up and cool down period (2 minutes each). After four weeks measurements of all study parameters were also taken of all the participants.

There were four consecutive sessions per week of training protocol.

DATA ANALYSIS:

The data analysis was performed on statistical package of social sciences (SPSS) 20 version.

To compare the effects of main variables of hypothesis repeated measurement ANOVA was used and its p-value was interpreted accordingly for within group analysis and Independent T-test was also used for between group analyses to find out that which intervention was more effective.

RESULTS:

Thirty young healthy females with age ranges between 20-36 years were included in to the study and divided in to two groups HIIT and MICT of 15 participants in each group.

Graph 1. Independent t-test for $VO_2\text{ max}$

This graph is showing that at baseline measurement the mean $VO_2\text{max}$ value of HIIT group was 47.340 ± 15.7319 and MICT group was 34.033 ± 6.6377 . The p value of test was ($p=.005$) showing significant improvement in significant difference in $VO_2\text{max}$ values between 2 groups. From the statistics it can be seen that MICT group has lower baseline value for $VO_2\text{max}$. After two weeks the mean $VO_2\text{max}$ value of HIIT group was 59.253 ± 18.1196 and MICT group was 37.400 ± 4.528 . The p value of test was ($p=.000$) showing that there was significant improvement in $VO_2\text{max}$ in both groups within two weeks. After four weeks, the mean $VO_2\text{max}$ of HIIT

group was 66.133 ± 15.0764 and MICT group was 39.653 ± 6.0932 . The p value of test was ($p=.000$) showing that there were significant improvement in VO_2 max in both groups. But the mean values of VO_2 max in both groups at fourth week are showing that there were statistically significant improvements in HIIT group than in MICT group.

Graph 2. Independent t test for RPE

This graph is showing significant improvements in rating of perceived exertion over a period of four weeks. At baseline measurement the mean RPE value of HIIT group was 12.53 ± 2.031 and for MICT group was 13.40 ± 1.121 and the p value was ($p=.159$). After two weeks the mean RPE value of HIIT group was 11.40 ± 1.298 and for MICT group was 12.27 ± 1.223 and p value was ($p=.070$). After four weeks the mean RPE value of HIIT group was 11.20 ± 1.146 and for MICT group was 11.93 ± 1.100 and p value of test at final assessment was ($p=.085$) showing non-significant results over a period of four weeks in RPE. But the mean rating of perceived exertion values in both groups showed statistically slight improvement in rating of perceived exertion in both HIIT and MICT groups, But there were more improvements in HIIT group than in MICT group in RPE within four weeks.

Graph 3. Independent t-test for RHR

This graph is showing that at baseline measurement the mean resting heart rate of HIIT group was 86.27 ± 11.659 and MICT group was 87.33 ± 11.004 . The p value of test was ($p=.799$) showing non-significant results. After two weeks the mean RHR of HIIT group was 83.80 ± 8.385 and for MICT group was 86.07 ± 9.738 and the p value was $p=.005$ showing non-significant changes in resting heart rate, But the mean resting heart rate of both groups showed statistically significant improvement in resting heart rate of HIIT and slight changes in MICT group.

After four weeks the mean RHR of HIIT group was 83.13 ± 8.408 and for MICT group was 86.47 ± 9.709 and the p value was ($p=.323$) showing non-significant results. The mean resting heart rate of both groups at fourth week showed statistically slight improvement in resting heart rate of both HIIT and MICT groups but there were more improvements in HIIT group than MICT group.

DISCUSSION:

The present study is on the comparison of effectiveness of HIIT and MICT in the improvement of cardiovascular endurance in young healthy females. The aim of our study was to find out the best possible training protocol to enhance cardiovascular endurance particularly in young healthy female population.

This study shows significant differences in cardiovascular endurance improvements in both HIIT and MICT groups. The results of our study have shown that there were more improvements in cardiovascular endurance in HIIT group than MICT group.

Fleg, *et al.* (2005) stated that VO_2 max is the most important indicator of cardiovascular endurance and mortality associated with cardiovascular diseases. It has been observed that VO_2 max gradually declines with age about one percent every year usually in second and third decade of life. So there is increased risk of cardiovascular diseases and mortality with increasing age.

Those individuals who have lower VO_2 max values at baseline assessment had more potential to increase their cardiovascular endurance than those who had higher VO_2 max values prior to training (Hickson, *et al.*, 1988).

Our study showed that at baseline assessment MICT group has lower VO_2 max value than HIIT group so it has greater potential for improvements in endurance than HIIT group. But in contrast to above findings, the results of our study had shown that there were more improvements in HIIT group than MICT group in cardiovascular endurance.

Talanian, *et al.* (2007) had found 2 weeks of high intensity interval training (HIIT) lead to an increase in cardiovascular endurance by 7_12%. It also depends on the participant's physical fitness and age. High intensity interval training is more beneficial, decreases the risks for heart diseases and decreases the resting heart rate than moderate intensity continuous training. The second parameter of our study was rating of perceived exertion. The results of our study have shown that there were greater decrease in exertional level of participants in HIIT group than MICT group that indirectly indicate the improvement in cardiovascular endurance.

The result of our study is consistent with the following study. (Racil, *et al.*, 2015) conducted a study by taking a sample of healthy females and randomly allocated them into two group i.e. high intensity interval training and moderate intensity continuous training group. The results of his study showed that there were significant improvements in rate perceived exertion in both groups but more improvements in high intensity interval training group.

The third parameter of our study was resting heart rate. The results of this study have shown that there was more decline in resting heart rate in HIIT group than MICT group that indirectly shows improvements in cardiovascular endurance.

Wisløff, *et al.* (2007) reported that heart rate adaptations were directly related to energy expenditure during exercise training because there was more energy expenditure in high intensity interval training than moderate intensity continuous training so there were more changes in resting heart rate at high intensity interval training as compared to moderate intensity continuous training.

LIMITATIONS:

One of limitations in our study was gender, only included female population so the results are only generalizable to active young healthy female population. Second was lack of availability of authentic measuring tools for heart rate continuously during training on treadmill and third was short time duration.

CONCLUSION:

In this population of young healthy active females the results had shown that although there were significant improvements in both groups but there were more improvements in VO_2 max in HIIT group. There was also statistically slight more improvement in Rating of perceived exertion and resting heart rate in HIIT group than MICT group. So in the light of improvements of above parameters it was concluded that high intensity interval training was more beneficial in improving cardiovascular endurance, decreasing rating of perceived exertion and also decreasing resting heart rate than moderate intensity continuous training.

REFERENCES:

1. Aghalinejad, H. & Gharakhanloo, R., 2005. The BMI, WHR, WC and percent of body fat norm in Iranian humans and their relation to heart and arterial disease. *Research Design, Physical Education and Sport Science Center*, pp.63-80.
2. Arena, R., Myers, J., Williams, M. A., Gulati, M., Kligfield, P., Balady, G. J., Collins, E. & Fletcher, G., 2007. Assessment of functional capacity in clinical and research settings. *Circulation*, 116(3), pp.329-43.
3. Burgomaster, K. A., Howarth, K. R., Phillips, S. M., Rakobowchuk, M., Macdonald, M. J., Mcgee, S. L. & Gibala, M. J., 2008. Similar metabolic adaptations during exercise after low volume sprint interval and traditional endurance training

- in humans. *The Journal of physiology*, 586(1), pp.151-60.
4. Cook, S., Weitzman, M., Auinger, P., Nguyen, M. & Dietz, W. H., 2003. Prevalence of a metabolic syndrome phenotype in adolescents: findings from the third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, 1988-1994. *Archives of pediatrics & adolescent medicine*, 157(8), pp.821-7.
 5. Cahill, C. 2014. „High Intensity Interval Training “. ChrisCahillPt.
 6. Dupont, G., Blondel, N. & Berthoin, S., 2003. Performance for short intermittent runs: active recovery vs. passive recovery. *European journal of applied physiology*, 89(6), pp.548-54.
 7. Fleg, J. L., Morrell, C. H., Bos, A. G., Brant, L. J., Talbot, L. A., Wright, J. G. & Lakatta, E. G., 2005. Accelerated longitudinal decline of aerobic capacity in healthy older adults. *Circulation*, 112(5), pp.674-82.
 8. Hickson, R., Dvorak, B., Gorostiaga, E., Kurowski, T. & Foster, C., 1988. Potential for strength and endurance training to amplify endurance performance. *Journal of applied physiology*, 65(5), pp.2285-90.
 9. Medicine, A. C. O. S. 2012. *ACSM's resource manual for guidelines for exercise testing and prescription*, Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
 10. Pelliccia, A., Maron, B. J., De Luca, R., Di Paolo, F. M., Spataro, A. & Culasso, F., 2002. Remodeling of left ventricular hypertrophy in elite athletes after long-term deconditioning. *Circulation*, 105(8), pp.944-9.
 11. Racil, G. et al., 2015. Rating of Perceived Exertion and Serum Leptin Responses to Maximal Exercise in Obese Female Adolescents: Effects of Exercise Training Intensity. 5th International Congress of Physical Education, Sports and Kinetotherapy, 2016.
 12. Talanian, J. L., Galloway, S. D., Heigenhauser, G. J., Bonen, A. & Spriet, L. L., 2007. Two weeks of high-intensity aerobic interval training increases the capacity for fat oxidation during exercise in women. *Journal of applied physiology*, 102(4), pp.1439-47.
 13. Wilmore, J.H. and Costill, D.L., 2005. *Physiology of and exercise*. 3rd edition. Champaign, IL: Human kinetics.
 14. Wisløff, U., Støylen, A., Loennechen, J. P., Bruvold, M., Rognum, Ø., Haram, P. M., Tjønn, A. E., Helgerud, J., Slørdahl, S. A. & Lee, S. J., 2007. Superior cardiovascular effect of aerobic interval training versus moderate continuous training in heart failure patients. *Circulation*, 115(24), pp.3086-94.